

Wiley Open Access Account Agreement

AGREEMENT DATE:	13 May 2013
PARTIES:	
Wiley Subscription Services, Inc. whose registered office is situated at 111 River Street, Hoboken NJ 07030, USA ("Wiley"), and	
Fonds zur Förderung der wissenschaftlichen Forschung (FWF) of Haus der Forschung, Sensengasse, 1 A-1090 Wien, Austria ("the Organization")	
MEMBERS	
Academic - means the students enrolled or accredited to the Organization and the teaching and research staff employed by or otherwise accredited to the Organization.	
<i>or</i>	
Corporate - every member of staff employed by or otherwise engaged by the Organization.	
<i>or</i>	
Societies - every current member of the Organization	
<i>or</i>	
Funding Organizations - every investigator funded by the Organization	
ACCOUNT DISCOUNT: 10% of the Article Publication Charge	
ADVANCE PAYMENT: €37.500	
COMMENCEMENT DATE: 13 May 2013	
OPEN ACCESS PRODUCTS	
The Wiley Journals published under the publishing program Wiley Open Access at the Commencement Date and to which new journals may be added from time to time: <i>Brain and Behavior, Ecology and Evolution, Geoscience Data Journal, EMBO Molecular Medicine, MicrobiologyOpen, Cancer Medicine, ChemistryOpen, Clinical Case Reports, Food and Energy Security, Food Science & Nutrition, Evolutionary Applications, Journal of the American Heart Association, Energy Science & Engineering, Journal of Cellular and Molecular Medicine, Microbial Biotechnology, Sexual Medicine, Molecular Genetics & Genomic Medicine, Journal of Medical Radiation Sciences, Immunity, Inflammation, and Disease, Cell Biology International Reports, Physiological Reports, Pharmacology Research & Perspectives, New Microbes and New Infections</i>	
SPECIAL TERMS:	
The parties agree to the terms of this Wiley Open Access Account Agreement which incorporates the Account Terms and Conditions attached (together "the Agreement").	
Wiley Subscription Services, Inc.	Fonds zur Förderung der wissenschaftlichen Forschung (FWF)
Position... <i>V.B.F. Director</i> ... <i>OA</i>	Position: President
Date <i>5/18/2013</i>	Date: 15/5/2013

Account Terms and Conditions

1. Definitions

In this Agreement, unless the context requires otherwise, the following expressions have the following meanings;

- 1.1 "Members" are those persons defined above;
- 1.2 "Article Publication Charge" (APC) means the charge levied by Wiley on the submission and acceptance of primary research material for publication in the eligible Wiley journals, the amount of which is dependent on the publication in which such material is published and the negotiated fee specified herein
- 1.3 "The Site" means the Internet Site at the URL www.wileyopenaccess.com
- 1.4 "The Advance Payment Fee" means the Article Publication Charge less any Advance Payment of Account Discount due for the material published by Wiley in an Open Access Product that is submitted by a Member or the Organization.

2. Wiley's Obligations

Wiley is authorized to collect payments under this Agreement both on its own behalf and on behalf of other Wiley group companies which own or publish the Open Access Products. In consideration of the payments made by the Organization and subject to the terms and conditions of this Agreement Wiley shall during the term of this Agreement;

- 2.1 Not charge Members Article Publication Charges for any primary research material submitted by a Member that is selected for publication in Open Access Products;
- 2.2 List the Organization on the Site as an Organizational Account holder;
- 2.3 Provide a link from the entry for the Organization on the Organizational Account List on the Site to the Organization's Website.

3. Editorial Independence

Nothing herein shall oblige Wiley to publish any article submitted to Wiley by a Member or the Organization. The Organization acknowledges that the selection of material to be published in the Open Access Products is entirely at the discretion of Wiley/the editors of the Open Access Products and the Organization waives any claim it may have against Wiley in the event that Wiley or its editors refuse or decline to publish any material (or part thereof) submitted by a Member or the Organization. An Article will be considered to be selected for publication once the author(s) has been notified that the Article has been accepted and Wiley has received the applicable publishing agreement for the Open Access Product signed by the rightsholders in the Article.

4. Terms of Publication

The Organization acknowledges that before any material submitted by a Member or the Organization will be accepted for publication the author and (if different) the owner of any copyright in such material will be required to agree to the applicable terms and conditions of publication (including without limitation the terms relating to Open Access).

5. Payment of Fees

During the term of this Agreement the Organization agrees to pay to Wiley the Advance Payment Fees.

The Organization agrees to pay to Wiley the Advance Payment on account of Advance Payment Fees due hereunder within 30 days of the date of this Agreement. The Organization may make additional advance payments at any time.

During the term of this Agreement Wiley shall after the end of each calendar quarter submit to the Organization a report detailing the balance of the Advance Payment at the commencement of the calendar quarter, the material published, the applicable Article Publication Charges and the applicable Advance Payment Account Discount deducted from the Advance Payment. If the balance of the Advance Payment is less than the balance due from the Organization for any Advance Payment Fees Wiley will notify the Organization and, if authorized by the Organization, will invoice for the balance due. If not authorized by the Organization, the submission(s) will not be published in the Open Access Products(s).

All amounts payable by the Organization under this Agreement shall be exclusive of any sales, value added or similar taxes.

Invoices are payable by the Organization within 30 days of the date of invoice unless otherwise agreed or stated on the invoice.

6. Term and Termination

- 6.1 This Agreement shall begin on the Commencement Date and subject to the terms and conditions contained herein shall continue until terminated by either party by not less than 30 days notice in writing.
- 6.2 Either party may terminate the Agreement at any time upon written notice to the other if the other party defaults by failing to perform any obligation on its part. The termination will become effective 30 days after receipt of written notice unless, in the case of a remediable default, during the relevant period of 30 days the defaulting party has remedied the default.
- 6.3 Either party may terminate the Agreement forthwith on notice in writing to the other if the other party is unable to pay its debts or ceases or threatens to cease to carry on business, goes into administration, receivership or administrative receivership, or any event analogous to any of the foregoing occurs in any jurisdiction.
- 6.4 Upon termination, and unless the Agreement is terminated as a result of the Organization's breach, Wiley will refund any unspent Advance Payment remaining in the Organization's account at the date of termination, and such refund shall be made within 30 days of the termination date. Any payment due to Wiley from the Organization at the date of termination shall be paid to Wiley within 30 days of the termination date.

7. Force Majeure

Either party's failure to perform any term or condition of this Agreement as a result of conditions beyond its control such as, but not limited to, war, strikes, fires, floods, governmental restrictions, acts of terrorism, public health emergencies, power failures, or damage or destruction of any network facilities or servers shall not be deemed a breach of this Agreement.

8. Notice

Any notice, request, statement or other communication to be given hereunder to any party shall be in writing addressed to the party as follows:

If to Wiley: Wiley Subscription Services, Inc.
 c/o John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
 111 River Street
 Hoboken, NJ 07030
 Attn: Rachel Burley
 Vice President & Director

If to Organization: Fonds zur Förderung der wissenschaftlichen Forschung (FWF)
 Haus der Forschung
 Sensengasse 1
 A-1090 Wien
 Attn: Dr. Falk Reckling
 Position: Open Access Head of Units

or mailed or delivered to such other address as each party may designate by notice given in like manner, and any such notice, request, statement or other communication, shall be deemed to have been given when received, except that if mailed by registered or certified mail, return receipt requested, or delivered by overnight courier service, it shall be deemed to have been given when mailed as aforesaid or when delivered.

General inquires about the Agreement or its administration shall be addressed to the parties as follows:

If to Wiley: Wiley Subscription Services, Inc.
 c/o John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
 9600 Garsington Road

Oxford, OX4 2DQ
UK
Attn: Natasha White
Associate Director

If to Organization: Fonds zur Förderung der wissenschaftlichen Forschung (FWF)
Haus der Forschung
Sensengasse 1
A-1090 Wien
Attn: Dr. Falk Reckling
Position: Open Access Head of Units

9. Liability

- 9.1 Neither party excludes or limits liability to the other party for death or personal injury caused by its own negligence or any other liability the exclusion or limitation of which is expressly prohibited by law.
- 9.2 Except as provided for in Clause 9.1 above, Wiley excludes all liabilities to the fullest extent permitted by law and in no event shall Wiley be liable to the Organization for:
- (a) loss of profits, business, revenue, goodwill, anticipated savings; and/or
 - (b) indirect, special or consequential loss or damage.

10. Governing Law

This Agreement shall be construed and interpreted pursuant to the laws of the State of New York applicable to contracts wholly entered into and performed in the State of New York. Any legal action, suit or proceeding arising out of or relating to this Agreement or the breach thereof shall be instituted in a court of competent jurisdiction in New York County in the State of New York and each party hereby consents and submits to the personal jurisdiction of such court, waives any objection to venue in such court and consents to the service of process by registered or certified mail, return receipt requested, at the last known address of such party.

11. Severability

In the event any provision of this Agreement is held by a court or other tribunal of competent jurisdiction to be contrary to law, the remaining provisions of this Agreement will remain in full force and effect.

12. Waivers

This Agreement constitutes the complete understanding of the parties and supersedes all prior understandings between the parties with respect to the subject matter of this Agreement. No modification, amendment, or waiver of any provisions shall be valid unless agreed in writing and signed by both parties. Any waiver in one or more instances by either of the parties of any breach by the other of any terms or provisions contained in this Agreement shall not be considered a waiver of any succeeding or preceding breach.

13. Assignment

Wiley may assign this Agreement to its successors, subsidiaries or assigns. This Agreement may not be assigned by the Organization, except with the prior written consent of Wiley.

14. Clause Headings

Clause headings are for convenience only and, being no part of this Agreement, shall not be used to modify, interpret or change it.